

Real-Time BIM–IoT Synchronization for Operational Digital Twins: The HPC4AI Data Center Case Study

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Abstract—Digital Twins (DTs) are emerging as a key enabling technology for the operational management of mission-critical infrastructures, where real-time integration between physical systems, Internet of Things (IoT) monitoring, and Building Information Modelling (BIM) can support optimization, predictive control, and sustainability. In this context, the University of Turin’s Computer Science Department is developing a DT of its HPC4AI data center, aimed at improving environmental monitoring, operational awareness, and energy-efficient management. The BIM model, originally generated from as-built documentation, was enriched to act as the geometric and semantic backbone of the DT. To create a live connection with the physical infrastructure, rack-level probes and environmental sensors are linked to BIM elements through dedicated shared parameters; this mapping is operationalized through a workflow based on Dynamo and custom Python scripts, which inject time-series measurements into the model as dynamic operational attributes rather than static annotations. Sensors inject timestamped measurements into a timeseries DB based on InfluxDB. Python scripts embedded in Dynamo periodically query InfluxDB via authenticated HTTP requests, parse the retrieved JSON data, and update the corresponding Revit parameters in real time, transforming the BIM model from a static geometric repository into a dynamic information system capable of reflecting the actual operational state of the data center. This process enables the representation of the current microclimatic state directly within the BIM environment. A dedicated alert engine evaluates incoming values against predefined thresholds and generates diagnostic flags and historical alert records. Graphical overrides highlight critical sensors through colour-coded states, allowing immediate spatial localization of anomalies. The methodology follows recent research trends demonstrating that BIM–IoT integration is essential for Facility Management-oriented DTs, enabling buildings to evolve into continuously updated, data-driven systems rather than fixed models. The paper discusses the system architecture, data synchronization strategy, and scalability for integrating additional sensors and control loops. Preliminary results show that the BIM–IoT bridge enhances situational awareness and lays the groundwork for predictive control and energy optimization of the data center infrastructure.

Keywords—*Digital Twin, BIM–IoT Integration, Real-Time Data Synchronization, Building Management System, Energy Efficiency, Facility Management*

I. INTRODUCTION

Data centers (DCs) are a critical component of the modern digital ecosystem, supporting cloud services, high-performance computing, and large-scale Internet of Things (IoT) infrastructures. Their rapid growth is accompanied by a

substantial energy footprint, with global electricity consumption reaching several hundred terawatt-hours per year and expected to increase further in the coming years [1]. Beyond the IT load itself, cooling and auxiliary systems significantly affect overall efficiency. The Power Usage Effectiveness (PUE), defined as the ratio between total facility energy consumption and the energy used by IT equipment, is commonly adopted to assess data center energy performance, with higher values indicating inefficiencies in thermal management and operational control [2].

Ensuring efficient and reliable operation requires continuous monitoring of environmental conditions, thermal loads, and technical systems, as even small deviations from optimal states may compromise performance and availability. The inherent complexity of data center infrastructures, characterized by strong interdependencies between HVAC systems, IT equipment, and spatial layout, calls for digital tools capable of integrating heterogeneous data streams with structured representations of the built environment.

In this context, Digital Twins (DTs) have emerged as a promising paradigm for operational monitoring and management. DTs can be defined as dynamic digital representations of physical systems that are continuously updated through bidirectional data flows, enabling real-time monitoring, analysis of system behaviour, and predictive decision-making [3]. Within the built environment domain, the integration of Building Information Modelling (BIM) and IoT technologies provides a solid foundation for Facility-Management-oriented DTs, allowing traditionally static building models to evolve into data-driven and continuously updated systems.

The paper focuses on the development of a real-time BIM–IoT synchronization workflow that enables continuous alignment between physical sensor measurements and their digital representations. Key aspects of the proposed approach include the system architecture, data integration and synchronization mechanisms, and operational functionalities supporting real-time environmental monitoring and energy-aware management. The proposed framework leverages a timeseries DB, automated workflows based on Dynamo, and embedded Python scripts to store sensor data as timeseries and periodically retrieve and inject them into the BIM model as dynamic operational attributes. This approach enables spatially contextualized visualization of internal conditions, supports anomaly detection, and enhances situational awareness for operators. In addition to detailing the system architecture and data synchronization pipeline, the paper clarifies the mechanisms that support extensibility and interoperability within the BIM ecosystem.

II. RELATED WORK

The application of DT concepts to the management of buildings and mission-critical infrastructures has gained increasing attention in recent years, driven by the need to improve operational awareness, optimize system performance, and support data-driven decision-making throughout the asset lifecycle [4,5,6,7]. In the built environment, DT implementations require digital representations capable of capturing both spatial configuration and asset-related information, making the choice of an appropriate modelling paradigm a critical aspect.

Within the AECO (Architecture, Engineering, Construction, and Operations) domain, BIM has emerged as a natural backbone for DT development due to its ability to represent geometric and semantic properties of buildings and technical systems. Several studies have investigated BIM–IoT integration to support real-time monitoring and facility management, demonstrating the feasibility of linking environmental sensors to BIM elements for indoor environmental quality assessment and asset tracking [8]. However, the literature consistently reports limitations related to interoperability, automation, and scalability, which often restrict the effectiveness of operational DT applications.

Recent research has therefore explored dynamic data integration strategies and bidirectional synchronization between sensor networks and BIM environments. Cloud-based architectures, time-series databases, and custom APIs have been proposed to enable near real-time ingestion and visualization of operational data within BIM platforms. Despite these advances, many approaches remain dependent on proprietary ecosystems, low update frequencies, or complex integration layers, limiting their adoption in data-intensive contexts such as data centers.

Beyond technical considerations, several studies highlight the practical challenges associated with DT adoption, including higher initial costs related to software licensing, sensor deployment, data management, and system integration [9]. While such investments may represent a barrier compared to traditional monitoring approaches, which are simpler and cheaper to implement, DT-based solutions can provide long-term benefits in terms of process optimization, predictive maintenance, and reduced operational costs, particularly in complex and energy-intensive facilities [10,11]. Conventional monitoring methods may still be adequate in small-scale or low-complexity scenarios, where the deployment of a comprehensive DT framework would offer limited added value relative to its complexity.

At the same time, the growing convergence of sensing technologies, data processing platforms, and digital models is fostering more integrated approaches to infrastructure management. DT frameworks enable advanced operational analysis but introduce increased data volumes, higher computational demands, and a strong dependence on sensor reliability. In particular, machine learning–based techniques, while promising for predictive maintenance and adaptive control, require substantial training datasets and careful design to be effectively applied in operational environments.

In parallel with real-time monitoring approaches, data center research has extensively relied on physics-based simulation tools to analyse energy performance, thermal behaviour, and cooling efficiency. Dynamic building performance simulation platforms have been widely used to model airflow distribution, HVAC system behaviour and hot- and cold-aisle containment strategies. [12]

In this context, the present work builds upon a research trajectory previously developed and applied to the HPC4AI data center, initially focused on the development of a dynamic thermal model aimed at supporting scenario-based analyses related to energy efficiency, cooling strategies, and sustainability-related performance indicators [13]. Within this broader research pathway, the present study builds upon and complements prior contributions by extending the simulation-centric approach toward an operational, data-driven DT framework based on real-time BIM–IoT synchronization. Rather than replacing physics-based models, the proposed solution introduces an additional operational layer that enables continuous alignment between physical measurements and their digital representation. In this perspective, simulation models support system understanding and scenario exploration, while real-time sensor data enable ongoing monitoring, validation, and future integration with predictive analytics and energy optimization workflows. This combined approach aims to demonstrate a pragmatic pathway for converging information modelling and monitoring systems into a scalable and operational DT ecosystem for data center applications.

III. SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE AND METHODOLOGY

A. Motivation and Objectives

The adoption of a DT for energy-intensive infrastructures such as data centers requires the effective convergence of two traditionally separate domains: (i) the BIM model, characterized by high geometric accuracy and rich semantic description of assets, and (ii) IoT-derived operational data, typically managed through external time-series platforms and monitoring dashboards. In energy management applications, this separation often leads to recurrent limitations: operational data are frequently detached from their spatial and system context, anomaly diagnosis requires expert knowledge of the physical layout, and communication among different stakeholders (facility managers, energy managers, designers) becomes less effective. For these reasons, this study implements a BIM–IoT integration workflow within Autodesk Revit, orchestrated through Dynamo and custom Python scripts, with the aim of embedding real-time operational data directly into the BIM environment. The methodology emphasizes modularity and interoperability, allowing heterogeneous sensor data to be ingested, processed, and mapped onto BIM elements. This design choice ensures that the proposed framework can be extended to additional sensor types and monitoring scopes while preserving the integrity and maintainability of the BIM model.

The proposed approach pursues the following specific objectives:

- Spatial contextualization of operational sensor measurements: to associate each of them with a specific BIM element (e.g., rack, room, or system) in a stable and traceable manner.
- Near real-time parametric updating: to write measured values directly into shared BIM parameters, transforming the BIM model into an operational view of the physical system.
- Integrated alerting and interpretability within BIM: to convert raw measurements into decision-support signals through configurable threshold-based alert

logic, complemented by immediate visual feedback and automatically generated Revit schedules.

- Reduction of operational ambiguity: to provide a standardized and shared informational language (parameters, schedules, and graphical overrides) that supports diagnostics, maintenance activities, and energy audits.

In this framework, the BIM model is no longer treated as a static design artifact, but rather as a context-aware, data-driven interface capable of supporting real-time monitoring and informed decision-making within the DT paradigm. The following sections describe the system architecture and methodological components that support this integration strategy.

B. Overall System Architecture

1) Architectural overview and design principles

The proposed framework is based on a modular and layered system architecture, in which each component is responsible for a specific function within the DT ecosystem, while preserving model stability, extensibility, and long-term maintainability.

The system is structured into four main layers:

- Physical sensing layer, responsible for acquiring operational and environmental data. A distributed network of environmental and rack-level sensors monitors key parameters relevant to data centre operation, including temperature, humidity, pressure, and other microclimatic indicators.
- Data management layer, handling time-series storage and querying. Sensor data are streamed to a centralized data management layer implemented through a time-series database, selected for its capability to efficiently handle high-frequency, timestamped measurements. This layer serves both as a real-time data source and as a historical repository, enabling retrospective analysis and supporting future integration with advanced analytics services.
- Integration and processing layer, implemented through Dynamo and Python within the BIM authoring environment. This layer is responsible for data retrieval, validation, preprocessing, and synchronization between the time-series database and the BIM model.
- Digital representation layer, where sensor data are contextualized, visualized, and interpreted within the BIM environment through shared parameters, schedules, and graphical views.

This layered approach ensures that the BIM model remains the central semantic and spatial reference, while avoiding tight coupling with specific sensor technologies or data acquisition protocols.

2) Data Integration and Synchronization Pipeline

Within the layered architecture introduced in the previous section, the data integration and synchronization pipeline operationalizes the interaction between the data management layer and the BIM environment. This pipeline is responsible for retrieving sensor data from the time-series database, processing and validating measurements, and synchronizing

the resulting information with the digital representation layer in a controlled and repeatable manner.

Sensor measurements generated at the physical sensing layer are continuously streamed to a centralized data management layer implemented through a time-series database.

Data retrieval from the time-series database is performed through a standardized API-based communication mechanism, enabling programmatic access to sensor measurements from within the BIM environment. Dynamo-embedded Python scripts act as intermediary clients that manage data requests and responses.

Requests are dynamically constructed using sensor identifiers, measurement metadata, and temporal parameters derived from the BIM model, while access to the data is handled through token-based authorization mechanisms. Retrieved data are returned in a structured format and subsequently parsed and processed within the Python environment prior to synchronization with BIM parameters. The integration and processing layer, implemented through Autodesk Dynamo and Python, is responsible for orchestrating the synchronization workflow. Dynamo provides direct access to BIM elements, shared parameters, and views, while Python enables advanced data handling capabilities, including dynamic query generation, sensor-specific time window management, and conditional logic. Importantly, each sensor is processed independently, ensuring that missing or delayed measurements from individual devices do not propagate inconsistencies across the BIM model. Validated values are then written into predefined shared BIM parameters, preserving semantic consistency and enabling visualization and alerting mechanisms.

The workflow remains inspectable, reproducible, and adaptable to different operational requirements. Furthermore, the reliance on standard web protocols and API-based communication ensures a high degree of interoperability, allowing the underlying data management system to be replaced or extended with minimal impact on the BIM-centric Digital Twin framework.

C. Sensor-to-BIM Mapping Strategy

Within the proposed layered architecture, the sensor-to-BIM mapping strategy represents the conceptual and operational link between the integration and processing layer and the digital representation layer. Its primary objective is to ensure that each sensor measurement is persistently associated with the appropriate BIM element, allowing operational data to be interpreted within their correct spatial, functional, and semantic context.

Rather than embedding sensor logic directly into the geometric model, the proposed strategy relies on a parameter-based association mechanism. Each sensor is identified through a unique identifier that is stored within shared BIM parameters and corresponds to the identifiers used within the data management layer. This approach establishes a stable and traceable connection between physical sensors and BIM elements, while preserving the integrity of the underlying geometric representation.

Mapping is designed to be independent of sensor technology and deployment configuration. Sensors may be physically represented within the BIM model when spatial placement is relevant, or logically associated with BIM elements through identifiers when geometric representation is unnecessary or impractical. In both cases, the association is

maintained at the parameter level, enabling consistent data synchronization regardless of the physical modelling choice.

From a methodological perspective, the sensor-to-BIM mapping strategy plays a central role in enabling higher-level functionalities such as operational visualization, alerting, and analytical reasoning. By anchoring sensor data to semantically meaningful BIM elements, the framework allows operational conditions to be queried, aggregated, and interpreted using native BIM constructs, forming the foundation for the alerting and visualization mechanisms described in the following section.

This approach is designed to be modular and reusable, allowing additional sensors or new data streams to be incorporated by extending the existing parameter structure and synchronization logic.

D. Operational Visualization and Alerting Logic

Within the proposed Digital Twin framework, operational visualization and alerting mechanisms are implemented within the digital representation layer, leveraging the sensor-to-BIM mapping strategy described in the previous section. By anchoring operational data to semantically meaningful BIM elements, the framework enables the transformation of raw sensor measurements into actionable information directly within the BIM environment.

Alerting logic is based on configurable threshold evaluation applied to synchronized sensor measurements. Threshold definitions are managed within the Dynamo-based processing layer, enabling adaptation to different operational contexts, sensor types, and monitored assets without modifying the underlying BIM model. During the data synchronization process, each validated sensor measurement is evaluated against its corresponding thresholds. By decoupling alert evaluation from visualization, the framework maintains a clear separation between data processing and representation, allowing alert logic to evolve independently of visualization strategies.

Operational visualization is implemented using native BIM functionalities, including schedules, view filters, and graphical overrides. Revit schedules automatically aggregate and display alert-related parameters, providing a structured and up-to-date overview of active conditions across the monitored infrastructure. These tabular views are not predefined but are dynamically configured through the Dynamo workflow, which allows the designer to define how alert-related data are aggregated, filtered, and organized within the BIM environment. This flexibility enables the construction of schedules tailored to specific operational needs and user profiles. In parallel, graphical visualization mechanisms provide immediate spatial feedback within the BIM model. Elements associated with sensors exceeding defined thresholds are visually highlighted through view-based overrides, allowing operators to identify affected areas and components at a glance.

E. Methodological Considerations and Scalability

Overall, the proposed methodology enables faster diagnosis of operational conditions, improves communication among heterogeneous stakeholders, and supports a more effective use of BIM as an operational Digital Twin rather than as a static design model, without relying on specialized external visualization platforms.

At the same time, the modular structure of the framework provides a solid foundation for future extensions, allowing additional functionalities, such as performance benchmarking,

anomaly detection, or predictive control strategies, to be integrated without rearchitecting the core system.

The following chapter applies the proposed system architecture and methodology to a real-world data centre case study. There, specific configuration choices, data aggregation strategies, and operational criteria are presented to illustrate how the general framework can be instantiated and tailored to a concrete operational context.

From a methodological perspective, it is important to clarify that, while the presented implementation relies on Autodesk Revit for the digital representation layer, the proposed BIM-IoT synchronization methodology is conceptually decoupled from the specific BIM authoring tool. Core components such as sensor identification, time-series storage, API-based data access, and parameter-based mapping can be instantiated in alternative BIM or digital model environments that support parametric attributes and scripting interfaces.

IV. CASE STUDY

The proposed BIM-IoT integration framework was applied to the HPC4AI (High-Performance Computing for Artificial Intelligence) data center located at the Computer Science Department of the University of Turin. HPC4AI was established to support the rapidly growing computational demands of interdisciplinary research activities, with a particular focus on artificial intelligence, data analytics, and high-performance computing workloads.

In addition to its operational role, the facility also serves as a research and development platform for experimenting with advanced technologies, monitoring strategies, and energy-efficient solutions. These characteristics make HPC4AI a particularly suitable case study for investigating current challenges, existing gaps, and emerging opportunities in the development of Digital Twins for data centers, as well as for evaluating the feasibility and effectiveness of a BIM-based approach as an integrated operational interface.

The specific objectives of the case study were threefold:

- to instantiate the general BIM-IoT architecture described in Chapter III within a real operational environment.
- to validate the robustness of the data integration and synchronization pipeline under real sensing conditions.
- to assess the usability and interpretability of BIM-based visualization and alerting mechanisms for operational support.

Accordingly, the case study focuses on the practical configuration of the proposed framework and its behaviour under real operational constraints, highlighting both observed benefits and implementation-related considerations.

A. Facility Overview

The facility is hosted in a custom-designed data center with an installed power capacity of approximately 250 kVA, engineered in accordance with Tier-III availability principles. The data hall comprises 16 server racks, each equipped with two Power Distribution Units (PDUs) capable of monitoring electrical loads at the phase level. Server connections are arranged to balance loads across the three electrical phases, while the Building Management System (BMS) continuously monitors power consumption at the level of the distribution

transformer. This configuration enables real-time estimation of PUE and supports detailed analysis of energy efficiency across the infrastructure.

From a spatial and thermal perspective, the DC adopts a hot-aisle/cold-aisle layout with a centrally located hot aisle flanked by eight racks on each side. The hot aisle is physically isolated from the surrounding cold aisles through a dedicated containment system, preventing air mixing and enabling controlled extraction of warm exhaust air. Cold air is supplied from above to the cold aisle areas. This layout enhances airflow separation, reduces recirculation phenomena, and contributes to lower fan energy consumption and improved cooling efficiency.

Cooling is provided by two roof-mounted adiabatic chillers operating under multiple modes depending on external climatic conditions. The chillers can function in free cooling, evaporative cooling, or mechanical compression modes, with a strong preference for free and evaporative operation due to the favourable local climate, characterized by dry air and consistent wind conditions. This operational strategy contributes significantly to the overall energy efficiency of the facility.

The selection of HPC4AI as a case study was motivated by its combination of operational relevance, advanced monitoring infrastructure, and experimental nature. The facility provides a realistic yet controllable environment for deploying a BIM-IoT-based Digital Twin and assessing its potential benefits for energy-aware and reliability-oriented data center management.

B. IoT Infrastructure and Data Sources

1) Sensor network

The HPC4AI data center is equipped with a multi-layered monitoring infrastructure designed to capture operational, environmental, and air quality parameters relevant to both energy efficiency and equipment reliability. Monitoring activities are organized across three complementary systems: the Building Management System, IT infrastructure monitoring platforms, and an independent sensor network dedicated to environmental and air quality measurements.

Power and cooling systems are supervised through the Vertiv Critical Insight BMS, which provides continuous monitoring of electrical distribution and cooling equipment status. Electrical measurements span from the main distribution transformer down to rack-level PDUs, enabling detailed analysis of energy consumption and supporting real-time PUE tracking. On the cooling side, the BMS monitors air temperature and relative humidity at both chiller and rack levels, as well as dew point conditions, to prevent condensation risks and maintain safe operating envelopes for IT equipment.

To complement BMS data, a distributed network of environmental and air quality sensors has been deployed within the data hall and adjacent technical spaces. These include multiparametric sensing stations capable of measuring temperature, relative humidity, differential pressure, particulate matter (PM1, PM2.5, PM4, and PM10) and gaseous pollutants such as CO₂, total volatile organic compounds (tVOC), ozone (O₃), ammonia (NH₃), carbon monoxide (CO), and nitrogen dioxide (NO₂). These measurements are relevant for assessing long-term equipment health, airflow effectiveness and indoor environmental quality.

2) Data acquisition and management

All sensor measurements are streamed to a centralized data management layer implemented through a timeseries database (InfluxDB). This database acts as the primary repository for operational data, storing time-stamped measurements together with sensor identifiers and contextual metadata.

Data ingestion is performed continuously, enabling near real-time availability of measurements for downstream processing. The use of a timeseries database allows both access to the most recent values and retrospective analysis over configurable temporal windows, supporting both operational monitoring and post hoc evaluation.

Within the scope of this case study, the database serves as the authoritative source of operational data. The BIM environment does not directly interface with physical sensors, but instead retrieves data through the integration pipeline described in the previous section.

C. BIM Model

The BIM model adopted as the digital counterpart of the HPC4AI data center was developed from as-built CAD documentation and technical system schematics. It is continuously updated and refined to accommodate emerging operational requirements and evolving DT functionalities. This iterative modelling process enables the BIM environment to progressively incorporate new data structures, parameter sets, and monitoring needs as they arise during deployment and operation, while preserving a consistent semantic framework. The model represents the architectural layout of the facility, the spatial arrangement of server racks, and the main technical elements relevant to airflow behaviour and environmental monitoring. A moderate Level of Detail (LOD) was selected to balance geometric fidelity and model manageability, ensuring accurate spatial representation and reliable element identification without introducing unnecessary complexity or computational overhead.

Custom parametric BIM families were developed to represent the different types of environmental and operational sensors deployed in the DC. These families are part of a structured sensor network, which includes:

- Rack-level environmental sensors.
- Air quality sensors: distributed across the cold aisle, hot aisle, control room and adjacent corridor.
- Rooftop weather station providing outdoor boundary conditions.

Each sensor family is enriched with a structured set of shared parameters designed to store real-time measurements and status information, acting as data endpoints within the BIM environment. The parameter schema includes unique sensor identifiers, live measurement values, timestamps, and diagnostic indicators, enabling continuous injection of monitoring data and allowing each sensor to function as an active, data-bearing component rather than a purely geometric object. An example of the parameter schema adopted is reported in Table I, illustrating the range of environmental variables integrated within the Rack-Sensor family. This parameter-based approach supports flexibility and scalability, allowing new sensors or monitored variables to be incorporated by extending parameter sets and mapping rules, without requiring structural modifications to the geometric model.

TABLE I. SHARED PARAMETERS OF RACK ENVIRONMENTAL SENSOR

SensorId	Last seen	Temp.	HR	DP	Alert
e.g., Rack1...Rack16	YYYY-mm-dd hh:mm:ss	°C	%	°C	YES/NO

D. Deployment of the BIM-IoT Workflow

The BIM-IoT synchronization workflow described in Chapter III was deployed on the HPC4AI case study to enable continuous integration of live sensor data into the BIM model. The workflow is implemented within Autodesk Dynamo and operates as an intermediary integration layer between the time-series database and the BIM model. Its primary responsibilities include: (i) associating physical sensors with BIM elements, (ii) retrieving and validating operational data, and (iii) updating BIM parameters in a consistent and repeatable manner.

1) Sensor-to-BIM mapping instantiation

In the specific case of the HPC4AI, each deployed sensor is associated with a corresponding BIM element through a parameter-based mapping mechanism. The mapping relies on unique sensor identifiers that are consistently used across the sensing infrastructure, the data management layer, and the BIM environment. This approach enables straightforward reconfiguration when sensors are added, relocated, or replaced, without requiring modifications to the Dynamo workflow itself. This structured mapping ensures that each measurement is interpreted within its correct spatial and functional context, forming the basis for downstream alerting and visualization mechanisms.

2) Dynamo workflow configuration

The Dynamo workflow is organized into modular functional blocks (Fig.1), each responsible for a specific step of the data integration and synchronization process, including data acquisition, validation, and persistence within the BIM model's parametric schema. This modularity facilitates debugging and supports incremental extension of the workflow as monitoring requirements evolve.

Fig. 1. Overview of the Dynamo-based integration workflow.

a) Sensor-BIM Mapping

The correspondence between physical sensors and BIM objects is instantiated via a shared parameter (e.g., SensorId) embedded in families. In Dynamo, we can filter elements by category and/or parameter we choose, yielding two aligned lists: one of Revit elements and one of their identifiers (e.g., Rack1...Rack16). Preserving alignment between elements and IDs is essential for deterministic writes and for minimizing the complexity of subsequent update operations.

b) InfluxDB Reading and Preprocessing

Time-series interrogation is implemented with a Python script executed within Dynamo. The query uses a tag key (e.g., SensorId) to identify each sensor stream and retrieve the variables of interest (e.g., Temperature, Relative Humidity, and Dew Point) over a configurable temporal window (e.g., 7 days). Signals are then aggregated at x-minute intervals (e.g., 5-minute) to attenuate noise and redundancy, yielding a cleaned, temporally aligned dataset for downstream interpretation. Consistency between tag keys defined in the Dynamo workflow and those used in the time-series database schema is required to ensure correct mapping between BIM parameters and database series.

3) Parameter setup and update logic

A second Python script updates the operational state in the model by writing “live” values and metadata to the parameters of sensor families.

The deployment of the BIM-IoT workflow establishes the operational foundation upon which alerting, aggregation, and visualization strategies are implemented. The following section details how threshold-based alert logic is configured and how operational conditions are aggregated to support effective interpretation within the BIM-based Digital Twin.

E. Alert Configuration and Aggregation Strategy

Reporting is handled by dedicated drafting views, e.g., Temperature, Relative Humidity (RH), Dew Point (DP), populated by a script that first detects alert conditions on the aggregated signals and then groups detections into episodes. The alert taxonomy, aligned with ASHRAE recommendations for IT environments [14], comprises:

- TEMP_HIGH ($T \geq 27$ °C).
- RH_OUT ($RH < 20\%$ or $> 80\%$).
- DP_HIGH ($DP \geq 16$ °C).
- DT_SPIKE ($\Delta T \geq 3$ °C between consecutive samples).
- SENSOR_OFF (no data > 15 min).
- OUTLIER (rack $T \geq +4$ °C relative to the rack median).
- STATIC_DATA (no significant variation for at least N hours; e.g., 12 h with flatness thresholds of 0.2 °C / 2% / 0.2 °C).

Thresholds (e.g., 27 °C, 20–80 % RH, 16 °C DP), aggregation cadence, episode continuity (i.e., maxGapMinutes), minimum episode length, and the *STATIC_DATA* window and flatness deltas are exposed as graph inputs. This enables policy-driven tuning without code changes. Table II summarizes the alert taxonomy adopted in this study, linking each event type to its triggering rule, default severity, and evaluation window. Detections are emitted as a flat list of events: ISO timestamp, rack, field, direction, value, threshold, type, severity.

TABLE II. ALERT TAXONOMY

Type	Condition	Severity	Window
TEMP HIGH	$T \geq 27\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ ($\geq 30\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ instant)	CRIT	5 min
DP HIGH	$DP \geq 16\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$	CRIT	5 min
RH OUT	$RH < 20\%$ or $> 80\%$	WARN \rightarrow CRIT if persistent	10–30 min
DT SPIKE	$\Delta T \geq 3\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ in 10 min	WARN	instant
SENSOR OFF	no data > 15 min	CRIT	15 min
OUTLIER	$T_{\text{rack}} \geq +4\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ vs median	WARN	5 min

Subsequently, events are grouped into episodes, sequences of consecutive occurrences of the same type on the same rack, subject to a maximum inter-sample gap (e.g., 10 min) and a minimum count (e.g., 5) to mitigate false positives.

Each episode is rendered as one table row with columns:

- Rack: BIM/DB identifier anchoring the episode spatially (e.g., Rack1...Rack16).
- Start: ISO timestamp of the first detection within the episode.
- End: ISO timestamp of the last detection; reported as ongoing if within the recency horizon.
- Type: alert class.
- Severity: operational criticality associated with the Type (and, where applicable, its persistence).
- Condition: human-readable rule string (mirrors detector thresholds).
- Window: temporal horizon used by the rule (e.g., 5 min, instant, 15 min, N h).
- Count: number of consecutive detections contributing to the episode.

Idempotence is ensured by assigning each row a unique key. On subsequent runs, keys are read (or reconstructed where absent) to avoid duplication. An automatic retention (e.g., 7 days) prunes out-of-window episodes, keeping views lightweight and focused.

F. Operational Visualization

The visual outputs are generated using native BIM functionalities and are directly driven by the parameter updates performed through the Dynamo-based workflow, without relying on external dashboards or proprietary visualization platforms.

Dedicated views were configured to support the visualization of operational conditions for different variables. Each view is associated with a specific monitoring domain and is populated through view filters and graphical overrides linked to shared parameters.

Graphical overrides are applied at the element level to visually differentiate operational states based on threshold evaluation. Sensors exceeding predefined limits are highlighted through color-coded schemes, enabling spatial localization of critical conditions within the data hall. This spatial feedback is particularly valuable in environments with dense equipment arrangements, where tabular data alone may be insufficient for rapid diagnosis.

Figure 2 illustrates an example of this native BIM-based visualization, showing server racks dynamically highlighted according to their real-time temperature conditions.

In this case, where we have sensors mounted on racks, the visualization layer is further refined through the Dynamo workflow by resolving the host element (i.e., the server rack)

and propagating selected measurements onto dedicated rack-level parameters (i.e., Rack_Temp_Live). This approach enables threshold-based graphical overrides to act directly on rack elements, which are more visually salient within the spatial layout, rather than solely on sensor. As a result, thermal conditions are represented in a clearer and more spatially grounded manner, while the underlying parametric state of sensor-level data is preserved for subsequent analysis, traceability, and auditability. Figure 3 illustrates this propagation mechanism, showing how live measurements imported from the IoT infrastructure are stored as parameters within the properties of the corresponding BIM elements.

Fig. 2. BIM-based visualization of real-time rack temperature conditions using native Revit filters and graphical overrides.

Fig. 3. Property panels of a rack-mounted sensor (left) and its corresponding server rack (right).

G. Case Study Discussion and Transferability

The results of the case study demonstrate the system's ability to consistently represent, organize, and communicate operational information in a form that is directly actionable within the BIM environment. The combined use of spatial visualization and structured tabular summaries enables operational conditions to be interpreted within their physical and functional context, supporting effective diagnosis in environments characterized by dense equipment arrangements. While external dashboards are well suited for high-frequency data exploration, trend analysis, and large-scale aggregation, they typically lack an explicit representation of spatial layout and asset relationships. By embedding live sensor data directly within the BIM environment, operational conditions can instead be interpreted

in their spatial, architectural, and system context, facilitating faster localization of anomalies and improving communication among stakeholders with heterogeneous backgrounds. Moreover, operating within the BIM environment avoids the need to export geometric models to external three-dimensional visualization platforms, where models often act as static containers for externally managed data. In the proposed approach, the BIM model retains its role as an active digital representation of the physical asset, enabling operators not only to visualize real-time data, but also to directly interact with, query, and update the Digital Twin using native tools. This supports an integrated operational workflow in which the Digital Twin functions as an actionable environment rather than as a passive visualization layer.

Although the proposed framework is demonstrated through a single operational data center, the underlying methodology is not specific to the HPC4AI facility. Core components such as sensor-to-asset mapping, time-series data management, API-based synchronization, and parameter-driven visualization are independent of the specific data center layout, cooling technology, or monitoring vendor. Adapting the framework to a different facility would primarily involve reconfiguring the sensor inventory, mapping rules, and threshold definitions, while preserving the overall architecture and integration logic. This distinction between the general methodology and its case-specific instantiation supports the transferability of the approach to facilities with different scales, layouts, or HVAC configurations.

V. CONCLUSION

The proposed approach demonstrates how BIM models can be transformed from static design artifacts into continuously updated, data-driven representations capable of supporting operational monitoring and decision-making. By integrating time-series sensor data into the BIM environment through a modular and extensible architecture, the framework enables consistent alignment between physical systems and their digital counterparts.

The decoupling between sensing infrastructure, data management, and digital representation provides a robust foundation for extending the framework to larger facilities, additional monitoring domains, or higher sensor densities without rearchitecting the core system.

From an energy management perspective, while the present study does not quantify energy savings or PUE improvements, the proposed DT establishes the data integration and visualization backbone required to support energy-aware control strategies and to evaluate their impact in future studies.

Finally, the structured integration of operational data within the BIM environment lays the groundwork for future extensions toward advanced analytics, including performance benchmarking, anomaly detection, and predictive control strategies. These capabilities can be incrementally incorporated by extending existing workflows and parameter schemas, reinforcing the role of BIM as a central and extensible interface within operational DT ecosystems.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This work has been supported by the DYMAN project funded by the European Union - European Innovation Council under G.A. n. 101161930.

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